

Modulation of Cognitive Function to Acute Cold-water Ingestion

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Abstract–

A. Background:

The human body, chiefly composed of water, exhibits significant changes in dehydrated states, including a decline in cognitive performance. So far, researchers have shown that cognitive ability can be modulated by hydration, and there is a paucity of literature showing modulation of cognition after acutely ingesting cold-water. Hence, this study aims to assess and compare cognition by the Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST) among 3 groups after water supplementation: Cold-water ingestion, Room temperature water ingestion, and no water ingestion group.

B. Materials and methodology:

The study comprised 228 college students of both genders randomly divided into 3 groups (Group 1 = Cold-water ingestion group, Group 2 = Room temperature water ingestion group, Group 3 = No water supplementation group) with varying hydration status aged between 18-28 years and their cognition measures were assessed by Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST) after acute water intake as grouped above. The results were then analysed with ANOVA using SPSS software.

C. Results:

The mean \pm SD of DSST scores was 99.81 ± 0.67 , 87.31 ± 10.24 , and 62.67 ± 24.16 in the acute cold-water ingestion group, the acute room temperature water ingestion group, and the no water ingestion group respectively, with $p=0.00$ among the groups.

D. Conclusion:

Our results suggest improvement of cognition by acute cold-water ingestion, suggesting a relationship between cognition and temperature regulation.

Keywords– Cold-water ingestion, Cognition, Digit-Symbol-Substitution test.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water - an essential in everyday life, has several benefits on every system of the human body, including the renal, digestive, circulatory, and even respiratory systems. One such benefit indefinitely includes improvement of brain function. Since proper hydration affects neural conductivity, it is important for optimal cognitive functioning. The human brain is predominantly (65-85%) made of water. Cognition plays a pivotal role in daily life, from learning new things to retrieving memories. It also includes intellectual ability, understanding, language and communication,

judgment, attention, learning and memory, problem-solving, attention and vigilance, processing speed, executive functioning, etc., in its domains that help human beings to become good and able communicators.

Our body, chiefly made of water, shows significant changes in a dehydrated state. When doing cognitively challenging tasks, the brains of dehydrated adults display symptoms of greater neural activation, indicating that their brains are working harder than usual to execute the given tasks. This manifests as fatigue, change in mood, and a decline in cognitive performance of cognitive tasks due to the strain of dehydration [1]. Multiple studies on the effect of water on brain function have shown that even at 1% dehydration, performance on a serial addition task was negatively affected [2]. And at 2% dehydration, there was a significant decrease in mental performance. Thus, proving that water deprivation negatively affects cognition and motor performance [3]. Edmonds, C. J et al also noticed a negative correlation between dehydration and short-term memory, and visual analogy tasks in children [4], following which research by Booth P, Taylor, et al, that supplemented water to the school children, showed improvement in their cognition [5].

People drink cold-water quite often, especially in hot weather. Cold-water ingestion has shown hemodynamic changes that may have some clinical relevance [6]. But it is obscure as to how consuming cold-water affects cognition. Cognitive performances can be tested in various ways by assessing any of the cognitive skills, by using certain standardized tests like Mini-Cog, Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), and Mini-Mental State Exam (MMSE), etc, which are used to measure mild cognitive impairment. Through a set of questions and easy actions, these assessments measure cognitive faculties [7]. Digit Symbol Substitution Test (DSST) is one such cognitive assessment tool that assesses cognition by involving simple, easily understandable, and doable tasks. This test is extensively used as a screening tool for cognitive impairment in diabetes and dementia & as an assessment tool for many motor disorders and drug interactions with motor functions. ([8], [9])

So far, researchers have shown that cognitive ability can be modulated by hydration, and there is a paucity of literature showing modulation of cognition after acutely ingesting cold-water. Hence, in this randomized controlled trial, we evaluated the effect of acute ingestion of cold-water on cognition using DSST as a cognitive assessment tool.

II. METHODS

This is a randomized controlled trial, an interventional type of study conducted in the department of Physiology of the institution. A total of 228 college students in the age group of 18-28 years of both genders participated in the study, who were randomly divided into 3 groups by a simple random sampling technique using SPSS software. The 3 groups were as follows: Group 1 = Cold-water ingestion group, Group 2 = Room temperature water ingestion group, Group 3 = No water supplementation group. Subjects suffering from mental disorders, sensitive to cold-water, and any morbid illness were excluded from the study. The sample size for each group was 76. The variable used for sample size calculation was the DSST percentile scores. A pilot study conducted showed the scores of the Digit Symbol Substitution Test as 95 ± 0.00 , 90.36 ± 22.01 , and 88.59 ± 1.79 for group 1 of cold-water ingestion, 2 of room temperature water ingestion, and 3 of no water ingestion, respectively. Observing a minimum difference of at least 5 units between the groups (as reported by the pilot study), with a confidence level of 95%, and an alpha level of 5%, for a difference of Standard deviation as high as 11 units, a sample size of 76 in each group needed to be studied.

After obtaining institutional ethical clearance and written informed consent from the subjects, they were asked to refrain from food and beverages, including water, for 3 hours before conducting the study. The subjects were randomly divided into 3 groups using the software for generating random sequences. Group 1 was asked to ingest 300ml of purified cold-water ($4^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) before testing for cognition. Group 2 was asked to ingest 300ml of purified room temperature water before testing, and group 3 formed the control group to whom water was not given before testing. The 3 groups performed the cognition test - Digit Symbol Substitution Test immediately after. The DSST is a quick, paper-and-pen cognitive test that measures mental speed and is a reliable indicator of cognition. On a piece of paper, the numerals 1 to 9 are randomly arranged into 4 rows, each with 25 squares. The subject uses a number-symbol key that is provided at the top of the page to replace each number with a symbol. The digits 1 to 9 make up the key, and they are each coupled with an original, simple-to-draw sign like a "V," "+," "=", etc. Ten of the squares are practice problems. After being shown how the examiner would substitute the digits for the first 3 squares, the subject will quickly and accurately write down the equivalent sign beneath each digit for the next 7 digits as practice, without the timer being on. The timer is then started, and the subject is asked to fill the rest of the sheet at maximum speed.

The time taken to complete the test forms the score in percentiles. The scores are calculated by preset score values corresponding to the time taken, set by NIMHANS in their NIMHANS Neuropsychology Battery – 2004 Manual [10]. The maximum score of 100% corresponds to ≤ 121 seconds for males and ≤ 107 seconds for females. More the score, more is the cognition calculated to be. Hence, lesser the time taken, greater the score, and better the cognitive performance. This test is performed on all three groups as mentioned above, after giving proper instructions.

All the data collected were entered in an Excel sheet, and data analysis was done using SPSS version 26. Numbers and percentages were used to illustrate the demographic characteristics. The Shapiro-Wilks test was used to check normality of the data. $P\text{-value} < 0.005$ has been considered statistically significant. The comparison of DSST scores among the 3 groups of cold-water, room temperature water, and no water ingestion has been done using ANOVA followed by post hoc comparison using Bonferroni test.

III. RESULTS

A. Comparison of Cognition with Groups Using DSST Percentile Scores

- 1) *Comparison of DSST Score between the 3 Groups:* Table I shows there is a statistically significant difference in DSST score among the 3 groups of cold-water ingestion, room temperature water ingestion, and the group with no water supplementation group. F value between the groups = 118.118

TABLE I
Comparison of DSST Score Between the 3 Groups

Group	Mean	Standard deviation	p-value	F value between the groups
Cold-water ingestion	99.81	0.67	0.00*	118.118
Room temperature water ingestion	87.31	10.24	0.00*	
No water ingestion	62.67	24.16	0.00*	

*p-value < 0.05 suggests significant

- 2) *Comparison of DSST Score within the 3 Groups:* Table II shows that on comparing the groups individually with their cognition test scores, there was a statistically significant difference within them as well, i.e; Group of cold-water ingestion and Group of room temperature water ingestion has p-value < 0.05 ($p=0.00$); Group of room temperature water ingestion and Group of no water ingestion has p-value < 0.05 ($p=0.00$); and Group of cold-water ingestion by Group of no water ingestion has p-value < 0.05 ($p=0.00$).

TABLE II
Comparison of DSST Score Within the 3 Groups

Group	vs group	p-value
Cold-water ingestion	Room temperature water ingestion	0.00*
	No water ingestion	0.00*
Room temperature water ingestion	Cold-water ingestion	0.00*
	No water ingestion	0.00*
No water ingestion	Cold-water ingestion	0.00*
	Room temperature water ingestion	0.00*

*p-value < 0.05 suggests significant

IV. DISCUSSION

The study tried to explore the variations in cognition among the 3 groups of subjects (Acute cold-water ingestion group, room temperature water ingestion group, and no water ingestion intervention group). The study showed a significant increase in cognition with acute ingestion of cold-water, considering DSST scores, suggesting improvement of cognition with acute cold-water ingestion. Further, there is a statistical increase in DSST scores in the room temperature water ingestion group when compared to the no water ingestion group.

Our study is similar to various studies, one such done by Suhr, J. A., Hall, J., Patterson, S. M., Niinistö, R. T, et al [11], which checked for cognitive performance in healthy older adults by use of other cognitive performance assessment tests like Repeatable Battery for the Assessment of Neuropsychological Status (RBANS), the grooved pegboard test (GPT), and the trail making test (TMT) that showed a significant increase in cognitive performance and they concluded that poor hydration had a significant effect on performance. Their study permitted subjects to ingest water during fasting, essential for intake of medications, etc, which could bring a natural change to their hydration status. Their study did not provide subjects with initial acute ingestion of water prior to the commencement of tests for cognitive performance. Our study could be more accurate as our subjects abided by an equal duration of strict fasting without any exemptions. Moreover, we included a range of subjects not covered in their samples (aged 18-28 years).

Another study done by N. Neavea, A. B. Scholeya, J. R. Emmett et al, showed that Water ingestion improved subjective alertness, but did not affect cognitive performance in dehydrated healthy young volunteers [12]. This result could be due to the fact that they gave a very small quantity of water (150ml) to the subjects after the fasting duration prior to testing for cognitive performance by RVIP tasks. They also had a very small sample size of about 24 in total. At least a minimum of 300ml of water is required to bring about an improvement in cognitive performance, as substantiated by Edmonds, C. J., & Burford, D. ([4],[13]). Hence, the result of their study might be contrary to those of ours.

A study done by Ollie J and Nathan B M showed that the endurance capacity during exercise was increased after a bout of cold-water ingestion, which helped in lowering body core temperature [14]. To regulate body temperature, feedback mechanisms are mediated via the hypothalamus - inducing stimulation of the sympathetic nervous system, causing skin vasoconstriction and release of Epinephrine and Norepinephrine(NE). NE acting as both a hormone and a neurotransmitter. – contributes to cognitive aspects. Hence, acute stress of cold-water ingestion causes short-term improvement in cognition by the release of neurotransmitters.

V. CONCLUSION

The research conducted among college-going young adults showed a positive variation/improvement of cognition assessed by DSST with ingestion of acute water when compared with no water ingestion group, and a further increase of cognition scores in the cold-water ingestion group on comparison with room temperature water ingestion group.

A. Limitations

This study can be improvised by increasing the duration of fasting by up to 12 hours from the current of 3 hours, by determining their subjective thirst prior to commencement of the tests, by assessing a wider age group as a sample size, comparing for gender difference and using various other cognition assessment tests that target particular domains of cognition.

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